

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

ANNUAL REPORT

2021-2022

CONTENTS

01 Message from the
President

03 Vision

04 Values

05 Digital Library Federation

08 Grants and Fellowships

13 Partnerships

17 Publications and
Resources

18 Revenue and Expenses

19 Statement of
Financial Position

20 Sponsors, Members,
Fundors, Governance,
and Staff

Message from the President

This past year was notable for the rigorous focus on our future. Emerging from the constraints of Covid, we recently concluded a nearly yearlong planning process that focused on our strategic advancement, purpose, mission, vision, and values. Conversations about CLIR's vision were especially animated, and involved staff, Board members, alums of CLIR's programs, and longtime friends and supporters. In discussions of values that followed, our staff and Board agreed that the following were of special import: reimagination, intentionality, community, and empowerment.

Reimagination gives us the strength to take reasonable risks, question existing systems, and rethink our approach as we develop new collaborations and partners, and align for greater impact. *Intentionality* requires us to seek out new, diverse voices and perspectives for our programs and initiatives, and demands transparency in all of our efforts.

Community signifies our focus on building working collaborations of purpose and practice, and respectfully engaging with others with whom we listen and learn. *Empowerment* inspires us to facilitate access to and stewardship of history and cultural heritage, whether that of an individual or a wider community. We consider education and participation in one's culture fundamental human rights, not a perquisite.

Charles Henry, president

Interweaving these values in all of our projects and programs is essential and inspiring, and we will continue to frame our efforts on your behalf by these anchoring propositions.

As for a longer-term strategic roadmap, these are admittedly tough times. While we may be breathing easier now than in the depths of the pandemic, we know that viral spread can erupt at any time. Our aspirations are also conditioned by growing alarm over the acceleration of climate change and the scale of its impacts on humanity, cultural expression, and natural world stability. The norms and expectations we enjoyed a few years ago appear more ephemeral today.

To draft a future course, we have looked inward at our programs to identify emerging areas of focus and their potential for constructive influence. Two seem especially apt for this letter, as both exemplify decades of successful work and evidence new breadth and sustainability. The first is a planned large-scale expansion of our

programs for cataloging and digitizing hidden collections. The new project will focus on preserving and making accessible collections across Africa, to promote knowledge and understanding of and about the African continent and African diaspora, and their histories. The limited availability of digital resources about and by Africans hinders egalitarian access to information and knowledge advancement on the continent, while impoverishing our understanding of history and inhibiting intergenerational knowledge sharing. Led by African-based professionals, Hidden Collections Africa will directly support institutions and staff across the continent to meet urgent preservation needs, close gaps in the historical record, and make records more accessible to people around the world.

CLIR's leadership programs are a second area of focus with exciting new vistas. The Leading Change Institute (LCI), which supports hundreds of dedicated alums who promote and embody the qualities of sound leadership from a wide variety of positions and responsibilities, will go on hiatus this coming year as we substantively evaluate the program. Meanwhile, CLIR continues ongoing leadership initiatives such as the Postdoctoral Fellowship program and the Authenticity Fellows program. Going forward, we will be asking key questions: What are new qualities of leadership needed in a world of pandemics and climate disruption? What typically assumed aspects of leadership might need to be thoroughly reconsidered? How might traditions of promotion, prestige, and competitive metrics impede enlightened stewardship? How are characteristics of leadership translated across cultures and generations? Are there essential aspects of leadership that transcend regional, national, and ethnic interests? We look forward to continuing these conversations.

In this respect, the expansion of Hidden Collections and reimagining of CLIR's leadership programs augur a strategic arc for the organization: to learn from ideas and insights that are multicultural, multinational, and ethnically diverse, providing for a future that celebrates difference, ensures equality of access to knowledge, and facilitates participation in one's culture as well as an appreciative immersion in other resources of imaginative expression. We believe these opportunities are a human right, not the privilege of a few, and that all of our constituencies collectively benefit from this encompassing and embracing mission.

A coda to our values statement is a mandate to leave the world a better place than we found it—a tall order, but invigorating. We believe that this can be accomplished only when we extol a mutual dependence on our ideas, our diversity of interests and perspectives, our aspirations, and our collective capacity, guided by the shared purpose of bequeathing a just and equitable ecology, of earth and mind, for generations not yet arrived.

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads "Charles Henry". The signature is written in a cursive, flowing style.

With sincere gratitude,
Charles Henry

Vision

CLIR envisions a world in which information and cultural heritage are preserved, accessible, useful to—and reflective of—all people. CLIR believes that ethical access to knowledge and culture is a human right, as it allows us to understand our past and present selves even as we make our future. Fueled by this conviction, we build networks and partnerships to advance the preservation of, and connections to, the human record.

Because our future is collaborative and interdependent, we cultivate partnerships with an international network of libraries, archives, museums, governmental organizations, nonprofits, and educational institutions to create and preserve a commonwealth of knowledge. This knowledge is organized, sustained, and augmented by interdependent communities of practice and entrusted to them. CLIR addresses complex shared challenges that transcend disciplinary, institutional, professional, and geographic boundaries. Chief among them are the following:

The existential threat of the climate crisis on tangible and intangible heritage of groups or societies

The need for more inclusive and accessible historical, cultural, and scientific records that reflect the full diversity of human experience

The imperative to build and sustain robust and equitable systems for knowledge creation, organization, and dissemination

In response to the most difficult circumstances, knowledge—authentically captured, well organized, accessible, and sustained—is our most vital legacy for future generations.

Values

CLIR looks to the following values to guide our actions and the decisions we make for our programs and initiatives, our partnerships and community engagement, and our interactions both inside and outside our organization.

Reimagination

- We look at what could be and are willing to take risks in meeting that vision.
- We question existing systems and assumptions and develop new resources and ideas to benefit the people and communities we serve.
- We continually rethink ways we can collaborate, partner, and work with others to achieve greater impact than we can individually.

Intentionality

- We intentionally include multiple, diverse voices in the development and implementation of our programs, initiatives, and conversations, especially those whose voices have been kept hidden or silent in the past.
- We are conscious about the use of our own resources—people, time, and money—and their best use in pursuing our vision.
- We are thoughtful and transparent about the likely outcomes and effects of our actions, take time to regularly assess our impact, and adapt based on that assessment to ensure we are continually realigning with our vision and values.

Community

- We are grounded in and intertwined with our communities; we engage intentionally with our communities to advance our vision.
- We are part of many communities and seek to listen, learn, and lead as best serves those communities' needs.
- We serve as a convener: an inclusive and collegial place for practitioners, scholars, and others who share a common purpose to gather for creative, constructive, and respectful engagement.

Empowerment

- Empowerment is fundamental to sustainability. We do not cultivate partnerships that depend on our benevolence but empower our partners to continue work that benefits us all.
 - Recognizing that access to and ownership over one's own history and cultural heritage is inherently empowering, we work to dismantle systems that have historically separated people from their own cultural record.
 - Empowering one person, organization, or community can be a first step toward transformative, systemic change, and is a key means by which we strive to leave the world better than we found it.
-

Digital Library Federation

The Digital Library Federation (DLF) is a group of networked member institutions and a robust community of practice advancing research, learning, social justice, and the public good through the creative design and wise application of digital library technologies.

1619 to 2021: A Black Journalist Turns the Light of Truth on the History of American Race

Stacey Patton and Nikole Hannah-Jones open the 2021 Forum, DLF's annual signature event, with a conversation about what it means to be Black women journalists doing the archival work of reclaiming artifacts and stories on American race relations.

DLF Forum 2021

The 2021 DLF Forum and affiliated events took place virtually for the second year, featuring presentations, panels, lightning talks, and workshops that drew more than 1,400 attendees from 49 states and 36 countries. The Forum opened with a keynote conversation between Stacey Patton, journalist and professor at Howard University, and Nikole Hannah-Jones, Knight Chair in Race and Journalism at Howard University, Pulitzer Prize-winning *New York Times* journalist, and creator of the 1619 Project.

Stacey
Patton

Nikole Hannah-
Jones

Nisha
Mody

Three days of Forum programming followed, organized around the idea of sustaining the community. Feminist healing coach, writer, and librarian Nisha Mody concluded the Forum with her keynote, "Showing Up: Caring for Each Other During Messy Times."

LEARN@DLF

In conjunction with the Forum, Learn@DLF was held for its fourth year and featured hands-on workshop sessions where attendees gained experience with new tools and resources, exchanged ideas, and developed and shared expertise with fellow community members.

NDSA's DIGITAL PRESERVATION 2021

NDSA's Digital Preservation 2021: Embracing Digitality followed the Forum. Tonia Sutherland, assistant professor in the Library and Information Sciences program at the University of Hawaii at Manoa, gave the keynote talk, "After the Archives: On Living and Dying in Digital Culture."

COMMUNITY JOURNALISTS

Developed for online events in 2020 to continue the tradition of Forum fellowships, the Community Journalist program seeks to highlight voices of people who identify as members of a group or groups that are underrepresented among digital library and cultural heritage practitioners. Ten Community Journalists were selected to attend the DLF Forum and share their reflections on the DLF blog after the event.

“ Digital librarians are standard-bearers of the public interest in the present, and for generations into the future.

—2021 Community Journalist
datejie cheko green

DLF Working Groups

DLF's working groups represent a community of practitioners who collaborate year-round to solve problems in a variety of digital library subfields, from project management and assessment to labor and accessibility. Working groups are organized across institutional and geographical boundaries, and participation is open to anyone, regardless of institutional affiliation.

2021-22 WORKING GROUPS

Climate Justice Working Group

DLF Committee for Equity and Inclusion

Technology Strategy for Archives Working Group

Linked Open Data Zotero Group

DLF Project Managers Group

Born-Digital Access Working Group

Data & Digital Scholarship Working Group

Working Group on Labor in Digital Libraries

DLF Metadata Support Group

Digital Accessibility Working Group

Assessment Interest Group

DLF Museums Cohort

Digital Library Pedagogy Group

WORKING GROUPS HIGHLIGHTS

The DLF Data and Digital Scholarship Working Group hosted its fourth transatlantic skills exchange and networking meeting with Research Libraries UK's Digital Scholarship Network in March.

The Digital Library Pedagogy Group published #DLFteach Toolkit Volume 2.

The Born-Digital Access Working Group released three resources:

- *An Exploration of Access Systems Framework (version 3)*
- *Description of Born Digital Materials in Finding Aids Portal*
- *Legal and Ethical Considerations for Born-Digital Access*

New!

Two new working groups formed this year

DLF Climate Justice Working Group

Technology Strategy for Archives Working Group

Grants and Fellowships

Two national regranting programs for digitizing rare and unique content, a postdoctoral fellowship program, and a dissertation research program form the core of CLIR's grants and fellowships.

Top left: "Muses," Hale Woodruff, 1950–1, panel 6 of *The Art of the Negro* from Digitizing Hidden Collections: Amplifying Unheard Voices Project, "History and Culture Access Consortium for HBCU Museums and Archives: Lifting Every Voice." Top right: Collections from Recordings at Risk project "Unheard Voices: Digitizing the Oral Histories of Underrepresented Communities in Idaho. Bottom right: Group photo of CLIR Postdoctoral Fellows. Bottom left: Presentation by Susie Woo, 2005 Mellon Fellow for Dissertation Research .

Digitizing Hidden Collections

In 2022, CLIR announced the first grant recipients of the Digitizing Hidden Collections: Amplifying Unheard Voices program. Built on the earlier Digitizing Hidden Collections program, this competition focuses on projects that propose to digitize materials that deepen public understanding of the histories of people of color and other communities whose work, experiences, and perspectives have been insufficiently recognized. The competition supports the digitization of rare and unique content stewarded by collecting organizations in the United States and Canada.

Demiah Smith, scanning technician for Digitizing Hidden Collections: Amplifying Unheard Voices grant recipient Christiansburg Institute.

Forty-nine organizations located in twenty-one US states and four Canadian provinces are involved in grants awarded in 2022. Projects celebrate the voices of Black, Indigenous, and other people of color, Deaf and Disabled, LGBTQ+, and immigrant communities, often in intersecting ways, through contributions to art, public media, oral histories, and education.

ASSESSMENT

In May, CLIR contracted with Jesse Johnston and Ricardo Punzalan to assess stakeholder experiences of the first operating cycle of the new program. Their report will be published in 2023.

DHC SYMPOSIUM

Planning took place for a two-day event for grant recipients to share lessons from their project work and talk about what's next. The symposium, originally planned for November 2020 but postponed because of the pandemic, was rescheduled to be held in conjunction with the 2022 DLF Forum.

DIGITIZING HIDDEN COLLECTIONS 2015-2022

\$28 million
awarded

115
grants funded

2,081,272
pages digitized: serials,
manuscripts, scores, and
other bound volumes

81,219
individual photographs; also
microforms, negatives, and
stereo cards

12,089
audiovisual recordings and
2,208 additional recorded hours
of audiovisual recordings

151,885
magazine tear sheet pages,
5,773 quilts, 443 pieces of
artwork, 17,598 pieces of
ephemera, 9,866 maps, and
37,024 pamphlets

Postdoctoral Fellowship Program

The CLIR Postdoctoral Fellowship Program offers recent PhD graduates the chance to develop research tools, resources, and services while exploring new career opportunities. Fellows work on projects that forge and strengthen connections among collections, digital technologies, and current research. CLIR facilitates the application processes; fellows are then hired directly by partner organizations. Since the program's inception in 2004, it has supported 221 fellows at 93 partner organizations.

COMMUNITY DATA FELLOWSHIPS

In 2022, CLIR launched Community Data Fellowships, which are tied to projects that thoughtfully and ethically capture and share data relevant to historically underrepresented or misrepresented people, communities, and populations.

Such data could include digital or digitized records of researchers and community members, materials from community archives, information captured from the web and social media, and records of individuals or organizations. Projects focus on the collection, aggregation, descriptions, preservation, and use of data.

Six fellows were selected for fall 2022, and an online orientation for fellows and supervisors was held during the summer.

2022 Community Data Fellows

CURATED FUTURES PROJECT

In February, CLIR published *Curated Futures Project: A Third Library is Possible*. The project serves as a guide for GLAM professionals to navigate beyond discussions of decolonizing our institutions to begin taking practical steps to enact change. The collaborative projects not only speculate about aligning academic libraries with social impact, but also provide examples in a variety of mediums, including podcast conversations, gamifying digital humanities, and mapping visualizations.

ASSESSMENT

A research team continued work on a retrospective summary of the experiences of current and former CLIR data curation fellows. The report, which will be published in 2023, makes recommendations for improving the program now and also reflects on its future.

Mellon Fellowships for Dissertation Research in Original Sources

Mellon Fellowships for Dissertation Research in Original Sources were first awarded in 2002 to support scholars in the humanities and humanistic social sciences. Over the years, fellows have studied artifacts spanning millennia, including source materials ranging from rare books, printed records, and photographs to artworks, maps, musical scores, audio and audiovisual recordings, films, and ephemera. The program made its final awards in 2019.

SYMPOSIUM

In March, CLIR hosted a symposium for former fellowship recipients in St. Louis—the first in-person program-related meeting since 2020. Titled "Looking Forward to the Past," the symposium invited fellows to reflect upon their experiences and to share their insights on the future of global archival research.

CLIR is working with fellows on a publication compiling the papers and ideas that came out of the symposium. It will offer suggestions for ongoing support and programming for future graduate students doing archival research.

MELLON FELLOWSHIPS 2002-2019

258
fellowships awarded

1,750+
research sites visited in 86
countries and 42 US states

Materials studied
spanned thousands of years and
included every conceivable type of
original source material

Partnerships

CLIR cultivates partnerships with an international network of libraries, archives, museums, governmental organizations, nonprofits, and education institutions to create and preserve a commonwealth of knowledge.

“

Our future is collaborative and interdependent. We will work with our partners to address complex shared challenges that transcend disciplinary, institutional, professional, and geographic boundaries.

—Charles Henry

HBCU Library Alliance Partnership

In 2019, CLIR and the HBCU Library Alliance announced a long-term partnership to foster awareness of and access to the history and collections held by Historically Black Colleges and Universities (HBCUs). Work has centered around three collaborations: the HBCU assessment, Authenticity Fellowships, and Material Memory podcast. The HBCU Library Alliance is also a partner in planning for the emerging Hidden Collections Africa project.

HBCU ASSESSMENT

Published in March 2002, *Creating Access to HBCU Library Alliance Archives: Needs, Capacity, and Technical Planning* explores the common barriers and shared visions for creating access to archival collections held by libraries at HBCUs. It is one of the few reports that document the needs of HBCU libraries as they relate to archives and special collections.

AUTHENTICITY FELLOWS

The Authenticity Project is a fellowship program that provides mentoring, learning, and leadership opportunities for early- to mid-career library staff from HBCUs. Fellows are matched with two experienced library professionals who serve as mentors. The 2022 cohort included 10 HBCU Fellows and 20 mentors.

HBCU LIBRARY ALLIANCE TOUR

Created in partnership with the HBCU Library Alliance, season three of CLIR's podcast, *Material Memory*, takes listeners on a tour of six HBCU libraries, highlighting the people and collections, as well as the role that these institutions play in their communities.

Leading Change Institute

The Leading Change Institute is a weeklong residential leadership program of CLIR and EDUCAUSE. It is designed to serve emerging leaders in higher education, including CIOs, librarians, information technology professionals, and administrators, who are interested in working collaboratively to promote and initiate change on critical issues affecting the academy. Since its inception as the Frye Leadership Institute in 2000, 838 people have participated in the program, representing a broad range of both domestic and international institutions of higher learning.

Left: The 2020 LCI was postponed because of Covid but was able to hold an in-person institute July 12-16, 2021.

Digital Library of the Middle East

The Digital Library of the Middle East offers free and open access to the rich cultural legacy of the Middle East and North Africa by bringing together collections from 40 cultural heritage institutions. Developed by an engineering team from CLIR and Stanford Libraries, in collaboration with Qatar National Library, the platform federates and makes accessible data about the collections and is navigable in Arabic and English.

During the fiscal year, DLME completed improvements to the user interface relating to search capability, system performance, IIIF viewing, and site translation. There was also a focus on system automation for both indexing and reporting.

Two videos demonstrating the improvements were produced by DLME and made available on the [Stanford University Libraries Digital Library Systems & Services YouTube channel](#).

- [Spring Demonstration #1](#)
- [Spring Demonstration #2](#)

Affiliates

CLIR establishes collaborative relationships and cross-institutional initiatives with organizations that have similar missions in the pursuit of common goals. These relationships take many forms, including Affiliates, for which CLIR typically serves as a fiscal or administrative home. Affiliates have their own governance and mission; CLIR provides integrated services and access to tools, platforms, research, and expertise to reduce costs, create greater efficiencies, and allow affiliates to better serve their constituencies.

In August 2021, CLIR welcomed the Scholastic Commentaries and Texts Archive (SCTA) as an affiliate. SCTA is a community and web service whose aim is to connect and freely distribute the intellectual history of the scholastic tradition. The community adopts, develops, and publishes standards for semantically encoding texts related to the scholastic tradition.

In May 2022, LD4 became CLIR's ninth and newest affiliate. LD4 is a community that advances library and archival practice through a focus on linking and using data on the web to advance the mission, goals, and objectives of libraries and archives.

Iraqi-Jewish Archive

In 2003, a US Army team found a collection of more than 2,700 books and tens of thousands of documents recording centuries of Jewish life in Iraq in a flooded basement of the Iraqi intelligence headquarters. To ensure the survival and accessibility of the materials, the US National Archives and Records Administration and its partners preserved, cataloged, and digitized the books and documents. An online exhibit at ijarchive.org/exhibit-pages/discovery-recovery.html describes the collection and its discovery. Traveling exhibits were also initiated, although they have been paused until additional resources and support are secured.

In October 2020, CLIR signed a memorandum of understanding with the US Department of State's Bureau of Near Eastern Affairs to collaborate in seeking support for exhibits of the material, as well as for potential meetings, conferences, and symposia. Although Covid paused much of the momentum for planning a traveling exhibit and website redesign, meetings resumed in late 2021 and early 2022.

Publications and Resources

CLIR publishes reports, newsletters, blogs, podcasts, and other occasional items, driven by our research agenda and community interest.

Podcast

Season three of the *Material Memory* podcast, "HBCU Library Alliance Tour," spotlights several libraries at Historically Black Colleges and Universities to examine their collections and communities. Conversations throughout the eight-episode season address key questions: How do we tell the story of Black history from the archives? And how does archival activity shape how we interpret history? Host Sharon Burney takes the institutions' holdings as a starting point for broader conversations about the intersection of race, gentrification, and societal oppression, and how this affects not only the institutions, but also the communities in which they exist.

Pocket Burgundies

In December 2021, CLIR announced the first awardees in its new Pocket Burgundy publication series. The series will feature 20-50 page pieces that address current topics in the information and cultural heritage community. The five selected publications will be published in 2023.

In June 2022, CLIR launched a new call for proposals; four recipients will be announced in December 2022.

Reports

- *Creating Access to HBCU Library Alliance Archives: Needs, Capacity, and Technical Planning*, March 2022.
- *Curated Futures Project: A Third Library is Possible*, February 2022.

Revenue and Expenses

Revenue Sources

Expenses

Statement of Financial Position

as of June 30, 2022

CURRENT ASSETS	UNRESTRICTED	TEMPORARILY RESTRICTED	TOTAL JUNE 30, 2022
Cash and cash equivalents	\$1,275,039	\$6,760,558	\$8,035,597
Investments	\$447,068		\$447,068
Prepaid expenses	\$323,216		\$323,216
Accounts receivable	\$683	\$549,667	\$550,350
Total Current Assets	\$2,046,006	\$7,310,225	\$9,356,231
TOTAL ASSETS	\$2,046,006	\$7,310,225	\$9,356,231
CURRENT LIABILITIES			
Accounts payable	\$152,042		\$152,042
Deferred registration revenue	\$94,833		\$94,833
Accrued expenses	\$151,800		\$151,800
Total Current Liabilities	\$398,675		\$398,675
TOTAL LIABILITIES	\$398,675		\$398,675
NET ASSETS	\$1,647,331	\$7,310,225	\$8,957,556
TOTAL LIABILITIES AND NET ASSETS	\$2,046,006	\$7,310,225	\$9,356,231

Sponsors, Members, Funders, Governance, and Staff

As of June 30, 2022

Sponsors and Members

(as of June 30, 2022)

[^] *Sustaining sponsor/member*
* *CLIR sponsor and DLF member*
+ *DLF member only*

Alaska State Library
American University
Amherst College*
Arizona State University*
Atlanta University Center*
Auburn University
Bates College*
Baylor University*
Beloit College
Berea College
Bibliotheca Alexandrina+
Boston College*
Bowdoin College*
Brigham Young University
Brown University*
Bryn Mawr College*
California Digital Library*
Carleton College
Carnegie Mellon University*
Carthage College
Casalini Libri S.p.A.
Clemson University+
Coalition for Networked Information
Colgate University*
College of Charleston
College of the Holy Cross
Colorado College+
Colorado State University+
Columbia University Libraries*
Concordia University+
Connecticut College
Cornell University*
Corning Museum of Glass+
Council of Independent Colleges
Dartmouth College*
Duke University*
Emory University*
Florida Atlantic University Library
Florida State University+
Furman University
George Mason University
George Washington University
Georgetown University*
Georgia Institute of Technology*
Georgia Public Library Service+
Georgia State University+
Getty Research Institute+
Grinnell College*
Hamilton College*
Harvard University*
Haverford College*
HBCU Library Alliance

Indiana University*
Internet Archive+
Iowa State University*
ITHAKA+
Jisc
Johns Hopkins University^
Kenyon College*
Lafayette College*
Lake Forest College
Library of Congress*
Los Alamos National Lab+
Marquette University*
Marquette University
Massachusetts Institute of
Technology*
McGill University Libraries+
McMaster University*
Metropolitan New York
Library Council+
Miami University
Michigan State University+
Middle Tennessee State University*
Montana State University*
Mount Holyoke College*
National Archives and
Records Administration+
National Gallery of Art+
National Library of Medicine*
New York Art Resources
Consortium+
New York Public Library*
New York University*
North Carolina State University*
Northeastern University*
Northwestern University*
Oberlin College*
Occidental College*
Oregon State University*
Peabody Essex Museum Phillips
Library+
Pennsylvania State University*
Philadelphia Museum of Art+
Pratt Institute+
Preservation Technologies
Princeton Theological Seminary+
Princeton University*
Purdue University*
Reed College*
Rhodes College*
Rice University*
Rockefeller Archive Center+
Rockefeller University*
Rutgers, The State University
of New Jersey
San Diego State University
Sewanee, The University of the
South

Skidmore College*
Smith College*
Smithsonian Institution*
Southern Methodist University*
St. Olaf College
Stanford University^
Stony Brook University*
Swarthmore College*
Syracuse University*
Temple University*
The Catholic University of America
The Claremont Colleges Library*
The Clark Art Institute
The Huntington Library, Art
Museum, and Botanical Gardens+
The Obama Foundation+
The Ohio State University*
Tufts University*
Tulane University*
Union College*
University of Albany*
University of Arizona*
University of Arkansas Libraries,
Fayetteville*
University of British Columbia,
Vancouver*
University of Calgary*
University of California, Berkeley*
University of California, Irvine*
University of California, Los Angeles*
University of California, Riverside+
University of California, San Diego*
University of California, Santa
Barbara*
University of California, Santa Cruz+
University of Chicago*
University of Cincinnati
University of Colorado at Boulder*
University of Delaware*
University of Denver*
University of Georgia*
University of Houston*
University of Idaho+
University of Illinois at Urbana-
Champaign*
University of Iowa+
University of Kansas*
University of Kentucky+
University of Louisville+
University of Maryland at College
Park*
University of Massachusetts
Amherst*
University of Miami*
University of Michigan*
University of Minnesota*

University of Nebraska-Lincoln*
University of Nevada, Las Vegas+
University of North Carolina at
Chapel Hill*
University of North Texas*
University of Notre Dame*
University of Oklahoma
University of Oregon
University of Oxford*
University of Pennsylvania*
University of Pittsburgh*
University of Richmond*
University of Rochester*
University of South Carolina+
University of South Florida*
University of Southern California*
University of Tennessee*
University of Texas at Arlington*
University of Texas at Austin*
University of Toronto*
University of Victoria*
University of Virginia*
University of Washington*
University of Wisconsin-Madison*
University of Wyoming*
Ursinus College
Vanderbilt University*
Vassar College*
Villanova University*
Virginia Commonwealth University
Virginia Polytechnic Institute and
State University*
Wake Forest University*
Washington and Lee University*
Washington University*
Wayne State University+
Wellesley College
Wesleyan University*
West Virginia University*
Whitman College+
Williams College*
Yale University*

Foundation, Institutional, and Individual Support

The Alfred P. Sloan Foundation
The Mellon Foundation
David Rumsey
EDUCAUSE
Institute of Museum and Library
Services
Library of Congress
Samuel H. Kress Foundation

Governance and Staff

as of June 30, 2022

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for Information Collaboration
Northeastern University

Tess Davis
Executive Director
Antiquities Coalition

Kurt De Belder
University Librarian, Director of
the Leiden University Libraries,
and Director of Leiden University
Press
Leiden University

Kathleen Fitzpatrick
Director of Digital Humanities
and Professor of English
Michigan State University

Fenella France
Chief, Preservation Research
and Testing Division
Library of Congress

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Librarian, Publisher of Stanford
University Press, and Vice
Provost for Teaching and
Learning
Stanford University

W. Joseph King
Former President
Lyon College

Carol Mandel
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New York University Division of
Libraries

Max Marmor
President
Samuel H. Kress Foundation

Buhle Mbambo-Thata (Chair)
University Librarian
National University of Lesotho

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Dean of Libraries and University
Librarian
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Champaign

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Jennifer Ferretti
Senior Program Officer, DLF

Wayne Graham
Chief Information Officer and
Director of Informatics, Cultural
Networks, and Knowledge Systems

Josh Hadro
Managing Director, IIF
Consortium

Charles Henry
President

Olga Holownia
Senior Program Officer,
IIPC

Sharon Ivy Weiss
Chief Financial Officer

Louisa Kwasigroch
Managing Director

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Chief Operating Officer

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Outreach and Engagement
Associate

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Grants and Contracts Manager

Becca Quon
Program Officer

Diane Ramirez
Administrative Services Manager

Jodi Reeves Eyre
Program Officer

Aliya Reich
Program Manager for Conferences
and Events

Gayle Schechter
DLF Program Associate

Kathlin Smith
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Academic Innovation
The George Washington
University

Council on
Library and
Information
Resources

Annual Report Design by
Erin O'Donnell